

**STRENGTHENING THE RESEARCH CAPACITIES
FOR EXTREME WEATHER EVENTS IN ROMANIA**

SCEWERO

GA 101159497

**DELIVERABLE D2.1: DATA MANAGEMENT
PLAN (v1.0)**

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Disclaimer

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

The document was developed based on the [Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template](#) (Version 1.0, 05 May 2021) provided by the European Commission as a guiding document for Horizon projects.

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List of abbreviations

CA – Consortium Agreement

CO – Project Coordinator

CSR – Case Study Region

D – Deliverable

DMP – Data Management Plan

ECAD – European Climate Assessment and Datasets

EFAS – European Flood Awareness System

EDO – European Drought Observatory

EWS – Early Warning System

FAIR - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability

GA – Grant Agreement

GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation

GIES/IGSU – General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations

HE – Horizon Europe

INSSE – National Institute of Statistics in Romania

INMSS – National Institute for Health Services Management

IPR – Intellectual Property Rights

LST – Land Surface Temperature

M – Month

NMA – National Meteorological Administration in Romania

OA – Open Access

RCM – Regional Climate Model

PI – Principal Investigators

WP – Work Packages

1. Data Management Plan (DMP) and Updates

According to the SCEWERO project proposal and GA, the DMP will be periodically updated as relevant additional information becomes available during the project implementation and with the activities' progress. The DMP is planned to be a 'living' document that will be completed with new information to reflect the current state of the data. The final version will be delivered at the end of the project.

In SCEWERO, according to the GA, the first version of the DMP is implemented in M6 (D2.1 - Data Management Plan) and will be updated in M18 (D2.3 - Data Management Plan - Interim) and delivered as a final version in M36 (D3.1 - Data Management Plan - Final). The final version will outline the procedure for collecting, storing, evaluating, and utilizing the data generated by the project upon its completion.

Each version of the DMP will reflect the status of the project's data. The generation of new data, not foreseen in the project proposal or the previous versions of the DMP, will be presented in the updated DMP versions.

The project coordinator (CO), UBB, is responsible for writing and updating all versions of the data management plan throughout the project implementation period, but input from all partners will be requested and integrated into each version.

2. Data Summary

The SCEWERO project aims to harness the huge potential of networking for excellence through knowledge transfer and the exchange of best practices from top-class partners to CO. The ultimate goal is to raise the research profile of CO and its staff, including researchers as well as administrative staff. This project will strengthen the research management and administrative skills, which will contribute significantly to enhancing the excellence of CO researchers in the field of extreme weather events and their impact on society and various economic sectors (human health, agriculture, energy, tourism, transportation, etc.). This enhancement encompasses comprehensive analysis, forecasting and communication, leveraging the use of artificial intelligence (AI) models and approaches.

During the project lifetime, the consortium partners will decide on including any new robust datasets for being re-used if needed. The data flowchain is synthetically presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SCEWERO data flow chain

2.1. Types and formats of data generated and re-used in the SCEWERO project

2.1.1. Types of data re-used

Several types of data have been planned to be re-used to achieve the SCEWERO project objectives:

➤ **Weather, climate and hydrological data**

SCEWERO will re-use existing data such as historical weather, climate and hydrological data, climate projection data derived from RCMs, remote sensing data (LST), health data, available from open sources and from national data providers for practical applications during training sessions (for CO researchers) and summer school (for national and international students) (WPs 4 and 5), as well as for the research activities to be developed during the project implementation (WP7).

For the evaluation of heatwave, hydrological extremes (floods and drought) and compound events over the past, we mainly build on existing gridded datasets such as ERA5 reanalysis (25 km as horizontal resolution) for the historical period, and data from the Coupled Model

Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) global climate models and the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP) global hydrological models for future projections. ERA5 ([Hersbach et al., 2020](#)) was produced by ECMWF within the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S); additional gridded data sets for specific comparison, such as MSWEP ([Beck et al., 2019](#)) for precipitation, will be used. The detection methods and analysis that will be presented during training sessions and summer schools are mainly derived from ERA5 reanalysis.

The weather data to be used to detect the impact of heat events on human health, data freely available from the NMA or from international databases ([ECA&D](#), [Meteomanz](#), [Oggimet](#), [Allmetsat](#)) for the locations in the CSRs, will be used.

For the workshop on floods, we will use publicly available datasets and resources for educational purposes, provided by:

- European Meteorological Observations (EMO-1) ([Thiemig et al., 2022](#)): this dataset consists of daily spatiotemporal meteorological data at a 1-arc-minute resolution, including precipitation, temperature (minimum and maximum), wind speed, solar radiation, and water vapor pressure; the [data set](#) is freely available;
- The [Global Runoff Data Centre](#) (GRDC): the centre provides time series of in situ river discharge data shared by National Hydrological Services;
- The high-resolution pan-European hydrological reanalysis (HERA) ([Tilloy et al., 2025](#)): the dataset is the result of running the LISFLOOD hydrological model at a 1-arc-minute resolution with a 6-hourly time step, forced with downscaled and bias-corrected reanalysis ERA5-land;
- The European Commission, Joint Research Centre (EC-JRC) [LISFLOOD](#): this organization provides open access to tools for hydrological modeling, the Global Flood Awareness System ([EFAS](#) or [GloFAS](#)) and various drought indicators datasets in the European Drought Observatory ([EDO](#)).

To make it usable, the collected data from various sources will be homogenised to achieve common/compatible file formats and standard spatiotemporal resolutions, put in ready-to-use formats (e.g., raster-based) to be further shared within the consortium partners to be used during the project implementation period and beyond for both training sessions and summer schools to allow hands-on activities and for research activities.

Remote sensing data

LST data derived from Landsat missions and available from the United States Geological Survey (www.usgs.gov) will be re-used for the integration with air temperature, humidity and wind data for an advanced analysis of heat stress in the CSAs in the WP dedicated to research.

➤ **Health data**

Health data to be re-used includes anonymised datasets on daily mortality and morbidity data provided by national data providers in Romania: INSSE (<https://insse.ro/cms/>) and INMSS (<https://inmss.ro/en/>). They will be employed only for research activities and will be required from the national data providers on a request basis.

➤ **Other data**

During the project implementation period, various data for project management will be developed, referring to partner information, meeting agenda and minutes, project reports, conference or other scientific events presentations, tutorials and specification documents, videos, and photos from project activities and meetings.

2.1.2. Types of data generated

- (1) **Research-derived data:** data obtained from the research activity will include four types of datasets (WP7):
 - *(Bio)Climatic data* consist of datasets for heat-related events and thermal stress with specific indicators covering the historical period and the following decades; they will include various indicators (e.g., frequency, intensity, duration, cumulated duration etc.)
 - *Thermal comfort/stress perception* data based on crowdsourced data collected through the mobile app from the users, and through a sociological survey.
 - *Impact data* will include the relative risk of mortality and morbidity for specific weather conditions.
 - *Critical threshold data for health impact* will contain a set of weather variable combinations that lead to thermal discomfort and increased morbidity and mortality.
- (2) **Software development:**
 - A *mobile application* for collecting citizen perception on thermal comfort/stress;
 - A *platform* to integrate physical science data, health data, and socio-demographic data to provide early warnings for heat events.
- (3) **Stakeholder-collected information** will become available after organizing the workshop for stakeholders (public authorities and health system employees) and the webinars for media. Their requirements and priorities will be analysed and integrated into the impact scenarios for enhancing the EWS in Romania.
- (4) **Personal data of participants** to various events organised: summer schools, workshops, trainings, and scientific events organised during the project will generate derived datasets, including names, contact details (including email addresses), organisational affiliation, education background, personal identifiers, and financial information (e.g., bank account details) will be collected and processed in line with EU regulations. This data will be used exclusively for project-related purposes, such as issuing invitations, participation certificates, processing payments, and fulfilling other administrative or legal obligations. Access to this data will be strictly limited to authorised consortium members and will not be disclosed to third parties without a valid legal basis.

All personal data collected as presented in (1), (3), and (4) will be processed in compliance with the GDPR. Participants will be fully informed about the nature and purpose of data collection, and explicit, informed consent will be obtained prior to their participation in any project-related activities. The project does not intend to systematically collect any special categories of personal data, as defined under Article 9 of the GDPR (e.g., data concerning health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, etc.). A clear and transparent consent form will be provided to each participant at the initial point of contact and must be signed before involvement in any project activities. Data subjects will also be informed about their rights under GDPR, including the rights to access, rectify, or erase their data, as well as to withdraw consent at any time.

- (5) **Specific research results derived from hands-on activities** during summer schools and training activities. The activities during the training sessions and summer schools are not expected to produce any new datasets, but the results obtained can be further used for

scientific publications, theses or other professional reports of the participants in the training events.

2.1.3. Format and size of data

SCEWERO will use various digital data formats that will include but will not be limited to:

- Multidimensional datasets (*.nc; *NetCDF);
- Compressed files (*.rar, *.zip);
- Images: *.jpg and *.png;
- Model scripts and data processing codes, in open-source coding languages (e.g. Python, R), version control software (Git), and trusted repositories (e.g., GitHub.com, Zenodo);
- Multimedia files for video recordings – interviews for dissemination and communication, as well as for online webinars and workshops: *.mp4;
- Spatial data: vector data in ESRI shapefile/geodatabase format; raster data in GeoTIFF format;
- Tabular data: ASCII format (*.txt, *.csv), MS Excel (*.xlsx), Postgres databases;
- Text data/information (for project reports, newsletters, articles, tutorial for the mobile app, presentations, and other documents, containing text): Rich Text Format (*.rtf), Text (*.txt), PDF (*.pdf), MS Word (*.docx), MS PowerPoint (*.pptx).

The expected size of SCEWERO datasets re-used and generated is in the range of several gigabytes (GB), including all types of data needed for or derived from project implementation.

2.2. Purpose of data generation or re-use in relation to the project objectives

For the training activities for CO's researchers and summer schools to be organised during the project implementation, we shall re-use climatic and hydrological data to allow participants to practice during hands-on activities and sessions. They are associated with the project SOs to raise the research capacity and scientific reputation of the CO's researchers and to increase CO's international visibility through organising summer schools. We consider re-using open data derived from available external resources from various sectors, such as international databases (e.g., Copernicus, ECA&D project, EFAS, EDO, Meteomanz, Oggimet, Allmetsat).

For research activities, the data re-use aims to support advanced statistical analysis of heat-related events and calculate the relative risk of mortality and morbidity associated with heat events in the two CSRs in Romania.

During the research activity, we will collect crowdsourced data via a mobile application to be developed in the project (WP7) and through a sociological survey, which includes user demographics (gender, age), location for each dataset, and the thermal perception of the user at the reporting moment/location. We will also produce datasets regarding heat event features (frequency, intensity, duration, etc.) and their related health impacts (e.g., on mortality and morbidity), as well as a set of critical thresholds for the occurrence of these impacts.

To ensure a holistic approach, the collected health and perception data will be integrated with official, location-specific meteorological records available from the NMA, Meteomanz, Oggimet, etc.

During research activity (WP7), advanced statistical techniques (regression analysis and clustering) combined with AI algorithms will be employed to extract meaningful insights from the datasets and to ascertain the associations between recorded temperatures and other weather variables contributing to the thermal stress and resultant health outcomes, based on daily data. Potential correlations and interactions between user perceptions, meteorological data, and health within the Romanian context, mainly focused on the simultaneity of data available, will be further explored. Regarding extreme heat conditions, in order to better characterize heat stress (human perception of stress), we plan to build on composite indices that also consider humidity and wind speed alongside temperature. Understanding how individual and community perceptions align or diverge from empirical data can offer invaluable insights into public awareness, educational needs, and societal responses to changing weather and climate conditions. This endeavour stands as a significant stride toward harmonizing human experiences with weather realities towards more resilient communities. Moreover, it will allow the identification of a new set of weather condition thresholds for the two CSRs and the vulnerable groups, enhancing the reliability and applicability of the findings.

2.3. Origin/provenance of the generated or re-used data

(1) **Origin of the generated datasets:**

- *(Bio)Climatic data* consisting of datasets for heat-related events and thermal stress with specific indicators (e.g., frequency, intensity, duration, cumulated duration, etc.) will be derived from historical and RCM output data (ERA5 and CMI);
- *Thermal comfort/stress perception data* will be collected from citizens in Romania through the mobile app and from the two CSRs through the sociological survey;
- *Health impact data* (relative risk of mortality and morbidity) will be derived through processing historical observation and gridded weather/climate data and health data;
- *Critical threshold data for health impact* will be derived based on weather and health impact data;
- *Stakeholder-collected information* will be collected during the workshop from the stakeholders (public authorities, health system employees) and from journalists during the webinars for media.

(2) **Re-used data will be provided by** the national data providers in Romania or from online available authorised sources, as follows:

- *Demographic and daily mortality data* – INSSE;
- *Daily morbidity data* – INMSS;
- *LST* – United States Geological Survey (www.usgs.gov)
- *Surface Urban Heat Islands* and associated hot/cool spots – P4 and CO, from INTEGRATE project (www.integrate.indecsoft.ro)
- *Weather/climate observation data:*
 - NMA (www.meteoromania.ro): via DATA.GOV.RO portal (<https://data.gov.ro/>) or on a request basis;
 - Meteomanz (www.meteomanz.com) – available online;
 - Oggimet (www.oggimet.com) – available online;
 - Allmetsat (<https://ro.allmetsat.com/metar-taf/romania-bulgaria.php>) – available online;
- *Gridded climate historical data* (1 km spatial resolution) – NMA via DATA.GOV.RO portal (<https://data.gov.ro/>);

- *Projected climate data*: in addition to the already mentioned ERA5 ([Hersbach et al. 2020](#)) dataset for the evaluation of past heatwaves and hydrological extremes, we build on the 6th Couple Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6) data to derive future projections on the long term and on the C3S Copernicus seasonal forecast dataset for the comparison of dynamical seasonal forecast results to the Machine Learning based approach we'll propose during the training sessions;
- Apart from the data mentioned in the previous section, projections of socioeconomic factors (e.g., population, GDP) in CSV and NetCDF formats will form the backbone of the risk analysis presentation on hydrological extremes during summer schools.

The sources of *Meteomanz* and *Oggimet* data are original SYNOP messages collected from weather stations in Romania; the source of *Allmetsat* data is the original METAR messages issued by Romanian Airports.

Datasets to be re-used will combine fine-scale data and information from physical sciences (e.g., weather, climate and hydrology datasets) with data derived from social sciences (e.g., demography, health, and communication sciences information) to obtain health impact data.

Outside the SCEWERO project, the data will be useful to several key stakeholders in the Romanian Emergency Management context, to professionals and researchers in the health sector, to the local authorities in the two CSRs, and to the NMA and the GIES/IGSU to improve the national Early Warning System in Romania for heat-related events at the country level.

3. FAIR data

The data to be used in trainings or research activities of the SCEWERO project will follow the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability), EU standards and regulations.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Since the persistent identifiers will allow efficient and rapid identification of data locations and access to the data by researchers, practitioners, professionals, and stakeholders, as well as students, in a very efficient manner, all newly created datasets will be registered for DOI. As our first option is to share the SCEWERO-produced data through the *Zenodo* repository, all datasets uploaded will be registered for a DOI. However, in the case of the second option, discussions will be conducted with the data repository to ensure that the datasets are allocated a persistent identifier.

Metadata submission is a requisite for all research data, whether newly generated or re-used and must be recorded at the time of dataset creation or collection. The metadata will be aligned with established standards from data archive centres (e.g., INSPIRE, Pangaea), stored in a centralised metadata catalogue, and made open and accessible to all targeted audiences (researchers, students, professionals, stakeholders, etc.). This approach enhances the project's impact and ensures research transparency. Datasets metadata will be freely available under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or an equivalent framework. In accordance with the FAIR principles—particularly ensuring machine-actionability—the metadata will include, at a minimum, the following information: dataset description, date of deposit, Horizon Europe funding details, grant project name, acronym, and number, licensing terms, and persistent

identifiers for the dataset, authors and their affiliations. Additionally, where applicable, linking of the respective metadata to related publications and other research outputs containing persistent identifiers as well will be established.

Search keywords will be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility of data discovery and re-use, including author, year, research topic, or other free text such as heat waves, impact, heat stress/thermal perception, climate indices, health impact, risk, and *emergency*.

Moreover, metadata will be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed. This will be ensured by adopting a metadata standard.

In the case of multiple version datasets, metadata will be developed for each version.

3.2. Making data accessible

3.2.1. Repository

The data, along with the metadata, will be deposited in a trusted repository and on the project portal available at www.scewero.eu. A detailed analysis of the various data repositories will be conducted in M7-12, and we will select one or two for further discussions and arrangements. Appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where our data will be deposited are planned for M13-15 of the project. A list of data types, along with a detailed description of the datasets (metadata), will be prepared for submission.

The first option for SCEWERO data and metadata sharing is the Zenodo portal (an account for [SCEWERO project](#) has already been created) because a DOI is automatically assigned to both datasets and metadata, and the project team should not arrange it separately.

In case of a second choice, consultation with the repository administrator will be conducted to check if the repository ensures that the data is assigned an identifier and if the repository resolves the identifier to a digital object or the project team should arrange it separately.

3.2.2. Data

Project-generated datasets will be made available openly in specific formats, depending on the data types. Generated maps will be shared in various formats through a trusted repository (see section 3.2.1) and on the project website.

Data received from third-party institutions (e.g., health data, weather/climate/hydrological data) will not be shared directly unless the data provider allows it.

In case of restrictions imposed by the health data providers, regarding the use of data by solely the party in the contract (which will be the coordinator of the project), the project partners, in particular, will, where necessary, conclude a separate data processing, data sharing and/or joint controller agreement before any data processing or data sharing takes place.

Crowdsourced raw data collected through the app developed during the project implementation, as well as sociological data collected through the survey, including user gender, age, health, and location, will be anonymized before publication to prevent user identification.

No data embargo is currently envisaged. If necessary, such restrictions will be provided and detailed in the revised versions of the DMP.

Project-generated scientific data will be provided under a CC0 licence. However, depending on the various pathways of the thermal comfort/stress perception research, data will be collected during the project implementation, and certain data will be subject to restrictions on use. Access will be granted or conditioned upon meeting specific access conditions. In addition, Non-Disclosure Agreements will be used when appropriate and if the SCEWERO consortium considers outsourcing certain operations or sharing data with third parties.

No personal data collected from participants in the organized events will be shared.

At this stage, we do not ascertain the identity of persons accessing our data. Once available on a public repository, the project-generated thermal perception data will be available for re-use without any prior approval or evaluation/access committee in compliance with the Creative Commons license mentioned above (CC0).

3.2.3. Metadata

Metadata of the newly generated dataset will be made openly available under CC0.

Data will be available as long as the chosen repository permits it. Furthermore, the data will be available on the project website for at least 10 years.

In the final version of the DMP to be delivered at the end of the project, the consortium partners will agree on the procedures for data usage beyond the project's completion.

As previously mentioned, the data will utilise various standard formats, thereby third parties can use their tools or open-source tools for data usage (e.g. QGIS, ESRI ArcGIS, Geoserver for georeferenced data and standard editing tools such as MS Word, Excel, or their open-source alternatives for text or table data) (see data formats in section 2).

3.3. Making data interoperable

Data and metadata vocabularies used will ensure standardisation formats that will allow exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions and third parties. Data will be unencrypted and usable by open-source tools. In this respect, SCEWERO will use generally accepted standards and formats to organise and structure the data and metadata. Geographical data will comply with Open Geospatial Consortium standards.

The SCEWERO project will establish a new national set of thresholds for heat-related early warnings, which will be published as a vocabulary to ensure that values are understood. In terms of data formats, they will maintain full compliance with OGC standards.

Our analysis on extreme events is mainly based on existent datasets such as ERA5 ([Hershback et al. 2020](#)), C3S seasonal forecast data (<https://climate.copernicus.eu/seasonal-forecasts>) and CMIP6 projections ([Jukes et al., 2020](#)), as already stated before.

3.4. Increase data re-use

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on increasing data re-use will be outlined in the subsequent versions of the DMP.

Open-source software will be utilized as much as possible while reusing the same infrastructures as previous projects carried out by consortium members. Re-used data will be properly cited, according to rules established for existing work.

The data generated within the project will be made available under a Creative Commons license (CC0) and will be made available through a public repository and the project website and can be used indefinitely after the end of the project.

The provenance of data will be documented using metadata and, where appropriate, a read.me file describing the data will be provided.

Data quality assurance is to be performed by research team members, as well as through automated validation by the AI-driven algorithms for data generation and error checks.

4. Other research outputs

Research articles will be published in open-access journals. Where appropriate, datasets will be provided as supplementary materials (e.g., survey data, thermal perception data, etc).

Due to the project's specificity, numerous training materials (e.g., presentations and lecture recordings, where applicable) will be developed for certain WPs. They will be made freely available through the project website, according to the GA. For instance, all the presentations provided during the training sessions and summer schools on extreme events by CMCC will be made available on the project website (www.scewero.eu).

The mobile application developed in the project will be made available in major stores for Android (Google Play) and iOS (App Store) as free software.

AI-based algorithms developed during research activities on extreme heat events and their impact, when applied to Romania, will be made available on the project website as well as in a public repository.

5. Allocation of resources

The costs for making data or other research outputs FAIR in SCEWERO project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) are expected to be minimal. The costs for curation and preservation of data is estimated at about 2,000 EUR.

The open-access publishing fee for the research papers generated in the project is planned to be covered by the requested EC contribution and is foreseen as a direct cost.

In case of no free data available (e.g., health data from the CSRs), the costs for data availability and usage are covered by the requested EC contribution.

In the SCEWERO project, each individual partner will be responsible for data management and compliance with its own rules and national/EU regulations.

The project General Assembly will decide at the end of the project what data will be kept and for how long, depending on the GA and the selected repository conditions. According to the GA, P4 guarantees storage for at least 10 years at a very low cost, utilising its own infrastructure. Additionally, being placed in a free repository, the data will remain available after the end of the project based on the repository owner's policy.

The project platform will be hosted by P4 for at least 10 years and made accessible for National and Local Authorities. GIES/IGSU and NMA will be granted free access to the Platform and data

downloads for that time period. Algorithms developed within the SCEWERO project for data processing will be published as open-source software that third-party developers can re-use.

6. Data security

The SCEWERO project does not envisage generating sensitive data that can raise specific security issues. It does not have potential for military applications or elements that can harm humans, animals or the environment.

To ensure data security, all partners follow best practices for systems management. Data repositories curated by P4 are covered by the company's compliance with ISO 27001 standards. Research data provided through the project website is stored in a secured geospatial environment provided by P4, based on a GeoServer implementation with Postgres/postgis support. It is firewall-secured and accessible only via the project website. Project data stored on OneDrive provided by UBB (CO) is a space dedicated to voluntary data exchange from project partners. It is designed to facilitate collaborative work during the project implementation at consortium levels and is not public.

SCEWERO data will be stored by P4 for at least 10 years on its own infrastructure, with backup and high availability configurations. Also, research data will be curated and preserved in the project's database, following data quality, security, privacy standards, and relevant EU legislation. They will be stored in the public recognized and trusted repository recommended by the REA (Zenodo) based on a dedicated agreement.

For each partner in the Consortium, the PIs will ensure that all team members involved in project activities related to data collection are aware of, understand, and adhere to the regulations outlined in the current DMP.

After the project ends, the mobile application and the platform will be updated only if the technical organisational measures are met.

Data collected and re-used by each should comply with the principles and regulations of the latest version of the SCEWERO DMP. In the event that any practical issues regarding data handling arise during project implementation, they will be discussed during the General Assembly and Work Package Group Leaders' meetings.

7. Ethics

The primary legal concern is related to the processing and sharing of **personal data** collected from participants during summer schools, workshops, training sessions, and other scientific events, as well as the collection of data through the mobile application and the survey. As the project involves the collection of personal information (e.g., names, contact details, organizational affiliations, education, and financial details), all data processing and sharing must fully comply with the **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679)**.

Ethical considerations include the responsibility to protect participant privacy and confidentiality, ensure **informed consent**, and prevent the unauthorized or unintended disclosure of personal information. Moreover, the project commits to the principles of **data minimization** and **purpose limitation**, ensuring that only necessary data will be collected and

used solely for predefined project activities (e.g., issuing certificates, managing reimbursements, reporting, and identification of vulnerable groups for heat stress).

Potential **legal risks** involve:

- The risk of data breaches if proper technical and organizational measures are not implemented;
- Limitations on international data transfers, should any non-EU partners or subcontractors be involved;
- Restrictions on sharing personal data with third parties outside the consortium without a lawful basis or explicit consent.

Ethics-related risks include:

- The potential for participants to feel coerced into sharing personal data without fully understanding how it will be used;
- Reusing research data in publications or reports without appropriate anonymization or de-identification;
- To mitigate these issues, the project will implement strict data management protocols and conduct an internal ethics review before the commencement of data collection. All participants will be informed about their rights under the GDPR, including the right to withdraw consent and request the deletion of their data.

In the questionnaire developed, informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, and participants will be fully informed about:

- The nature and purpose of the data being collected;
- How their data will be processed, stored, and potentially shared (e.g., within the consortium or in anonymised form for scientific publications);
- The duration for which their data will be retained, including provisions for long-term preservation in accordance with institutional, national, and EU data management policies.

The consent form integrated into the questionnaires will clearly explain that:

- Data will only be shared in compliance with GDPR, and when necessary, will be anonymized or pseudonymized to protect participant privacy;
- Participants have the right to refuse data sharing or long-term preservation without any negative consequences on their involvement in the project;
- Participants retain the right to withdraw their consent at any time, as well as the right to access, rectify, or request deletion of their personal data.

All ethics issues related to personal data protection and AI-based algorithms will be assessed in the two ethical reports delivered by the external independent Ethics Advisor. Both reports are deliverables of the dedicated WP (WP1 - *Ethics requirements*) and are planned to be delivered at mid-term of the project and at the end of the project.

8. Other issues

In addition to the guidelines provided by this document, all partners will handle data according to the applicable European and national laws and regulations and accordingly with any internal procedures, guidelines and rules adopted and in force in their respective cases.

